

Quantum and Classical Mechanics and Two Delivery Schemes for Force Part II

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Newtonian mechanics deals with two types of force delivery schemes, one linked to the variable x and the other to t . They may be written as: $\int F dt$ (impulse) and $\int F dx$ (work) and appear to be symmetric in the two variables. The problem is that expressed in terms of dp one sees an immediate difference linked to discrete versus continuous change. In particular: $dp = F dt$ ((1a)) and $v dp = F dx$ ((1a)). ((1a)) allows for a discrete change in p in a tiny interval of time. "X" does not come into play at all in the equation and one might think of the impulse occurring at a point x . Due to the discrete nature of integral dp changes, one may think in terms of probabilities because a given p_A may have been obtained from discrete impulses: $p_1 \rightarrow p_2 \rightarrow p_3$ or $p_4 + p_5$. etc. The final p state is the same and so not only does there exist probability but also the notion of product probabilities such that $\exp(p_i b) \exp(p_j b) = \exp((p_i + p_j) b)$ where b is a constant. Given that $\exp(pb)$ increases exponentially, one might rather use the periodic probability $\exp(i p b)$. One may note how impulse type hits and their discrete momentum results lead to stochasticity in a Maxwell-Boltzmann gas.

The form $v dp = F dx$ is very different in that it does not allow discrete jumps of p because $v = dx/dt$. If one assumes a very large F at x_1 and $dx \rightarrow 0$ such that the product is not 0, one might consider dp changing discretely, but what is then used for v ? Instead one considers a range of x with a corresponding range in t such that $x(t)$ in order to compute v . Thus this is a deterministic situation because x and t cannot be decoupled. It leads to the notion of a kinetic energy $pp/2m$ associated with p . This kinetic energy is calculated by considering p change from 0 to p .

An interesting feature arises because impulse = $\int F dt$ may be thought of as discrete allowing p_1 to jump to p_2 . Nevertheless, the deterministic approach states there is a kinetic energy associated with p_1 and p_2 , namely $p_1^2/2m$, $p_2^2/2m$, even though no deterministic path in time and space was taken. The impulse was said to occur at x in a very tiny time range. Thus there seems to be a contradiction. $pp/2m$ requires a range of x and t with $x(t)$. The impulse only occurs in time, with x decoupled but there must be an associated x range which is then not deterministic i.e. a decoupled x range. This suggests a characteristic length associated with a momentum p in which one does not follow time deterministically. If one does not follow x in t in this special length, then one has a probability distribution. A similar argument occurs for time. Consider $F dx$ with time absent. If dx becomes very tiny and $F(x)$ very large, one may think that work is done at an instant in time, but there must be a time range for $pp/2m$. Thus there is a special time period not associated with x in which one has probabilistic behaviour i.e. not $x(t)$.

One may note from the notion of impulse that a given p may be obtained through different series of smaller impulses, e.g. $\{p_1, p_2, p_3\}$ and $\{p_4, p_5\}$. These are associated with kinetic energy series $\{p_1^2/2m, p_2^2/2m, p_3^2/2m\}$ and $\{p_4^2/2m, p_5^2/2m\}$. The final result is the same. Thus the discrete nature of changes leads to a probability scheme such that $P(p_1)P(p_2) = P(p_1 + p_2)$ and $P(e_1)P(e_2) = P(e_1 + e_2)$. This we argue leads to: $P(p) = \exp(i p b_1)$ and $P(e) = \exp(i e b_2)$ where b_1 and b_2 at first seem to be constant. We noted, however, that an impulse implies a probabilistic range in x and $F dx \rightarrow \text{finite}$ when $dx \rightarrow 0$ a probabilistic range in t . Thus b_1 may be replaced with x and b_2 with t . At any given point in time or space, x and t are constants i.e. b_1 and b_2 .

Next, we consider the situation of special relativity i.e. a Lorentz boost. We consider an initial state of energy = $m_0 c^2$, $x=0$, $t=t_0$ and view it from a frame moving at a constant velocity v . Although one may use infinitesimal velocities, a main point we wish to make is that special relativity allows for the use of finite velocities which give the sense of discrete changes like in the impulse case. This should again be associated with probabilities. Special relativity yields the Lorentz invariant $A = -Et + px$ where $v=x/t$. Nevertheless, x and t are written in the invariant as if they were independent. It may be noted that $dA=0$ if t changes on its own as \hbar/E and x on its own as \hbar/p . Thus one may obtain specific x and t probability ranges. This is again consistent with the probabilistic picture or $\exp(-iEt)$ and $\exp(-ipx)$.

It may be noted that even with the probabilistic picture, a particle with constant p moves deterministically on average as $x = p/m t$. If $x = \hbar/p$, then $1/t$ is not \hbar/E and if $t = \hbar/E$ then x is not \hbar/p . Thus the values \hbar/E and \hbar/p seem not to be linked with the current deterministic motion, but rather with the creation of p in the first place. $E = p^2/2m$ and this is obtained by considering p changing from 0 to p . Thus the "frequency" E seems to capture the information of the creation of p and we argue that the wavelength captures the creation of x as a probability distribution in x which one would usually associate with force/acceleration.

Newtonian Impulse and Work

Newtonian mechanics seems to treat the variables t and x in a symmetric way in the two force delivery schemes:

$$\text{Impulse} = \int F dt \quad ((2a)) \quad \text{and} \quad \text{Work} = \int F dx \quad ((2b))$$

The problem is that these two schemes are very different because:

$$\text{Impulse} = \int dp \quad ((3a)) \quad \text{and} \quad \text{Work} = \int p/m dp \quad ((3b))$$

Thus dp may change discretely in ((3a)) with no notion of x present i.e. a very strong F may combine with a tiny dt to change p_1 to p_2 presumably at a point x . This seems to be the notion of an impulse hit during two particle collisions in a Maxwell-Boltzmann gas because if a potential is present, one assumes that a collision occurs at a point x .

In the case of $\int v dp = \int F dx$, however, one cannot have a discrete change from p_1 to p_2 because one would not know what v to use. Therefore one must perform an integral and finds that

$$\text{Work} = p^2/2m \quad \text{as } p \text{ goes from } 0 \text{ to its final } p \text{ value} \quad ((4))$$

((4)) is thus calculated using the notion of determinism and infinitesimal continuous changes.

The unusual issue is that $p^2/2m$ is associated with a p . This p may be created by deterministically accelerating a particle from $p=0$ to p or by delivering an impulse. Given the result p , one has no idea how it was created. Thus $p^2/2m$ is associated with p in discrete hits as well. For example, a p_1 receiving an impulse and changing to p_2 means a kinetic energy of

$p_1 p_1/2m$ changes to $p_2 p_2/2m$. This, however, seems to lead to a contradiction related to x and t .

$F dt$ shows only t and so seems to be independent of x . $F dx$ shows only x and so seems to be independent of t .

An impulse which occurs as $dt \rightarrow 0$, but $F \rightarrow$ very large seems to indicate a hit at a given x point. The property $p p/2m$, however, cannot be associated with an x point, it requires both a time range and x range in which velocity changes. According to Newtonian mechanics v is a distinct value in each constant dx piece associated with a changing dt .

To deal with this contradiction, we suggest introducing a characteristic x length associated with p . The impulse, however, does take place in a very short $dt \rightarrow 0$ so t is decoupled from x and x must be probabilistic within this length., we argue. At first this seems to be very unusual, but it is not so if considered from the view of probability.

Probability Associated with Discrete Changes

The fact that an impulse leads to discrete p changes means one may have different sets of impulses create a given p i.e.

$$\{p_1, p_2, p_3\} \text{ or } \{p_4, p_5\} \text{ etc } ((5))$$

This suggests a probability weight for each set. In classical statistical mechanics, one assumes the same weight for different schemes as there is no reason to favour one over the other. This leads to the probability rule:

$$P(p_1)P(p_2) = P(p_1 + p_2) \text{ which is also associated with conservation } ((6))$$

Thus one has $\exp(-p/b)$ as a probability with b being a constant. This, however, grows exponentially with p so one might rather suggest a periodic function:

$$P(p) = \exp(i p/b) ((7))$$

One may then replace b with x in order to obtain the x probability distribution discussed in the previous section. One may note that t does not appear in ((7)), however, there is deterministic motion associated with p because it is a function of v and $x=vt$ deterministically. Thus on average deterministic motion also occurs, but within every \hbar/p region the particle position is unknown and governed by two probability distributions $\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$.

What about time? If one considers $\int F dx$ finite with $dx \rightarrow 0$ then this might imply $dt \rightarrow 0$, but it cannot because dp must lead to a finite change from p_1 to p_2 and this implies a range of values hence a range of t values. Thus one may think of a finite time range independent of x

which is probabilistic. In the impulse problem the momentum sets correspond to kinetic energy sets so there should also be a probability for energy i.e.

$$\exp(-i p^2/2m t) \quad ((8a))$$

One may note that ((8)) implies an impulse scheme. (Thus in a quantum bound state one considers a distribution $W(x) = \text{Sum over } p \ a(p)\exp(ipx)$. Neither time, velocity or $\exp(-ipp^2/m t)$ appear in $W(x)$ as the impulse picture $\int dp = \int F dt$ does not contain t explicitly. Nevertheless, the notion of ((8)) does not disappear, because: $-1/2m \ d/dx \ dW/dx / W + V(x) = E_n$ and $\exp(-iE_n t)$ describes the bound system.

Special Relativity

Interestingly, the same ideas appear in special relativity because it also allows for discrete jumps. Consider the state energy= $m\phi c^2$, $x=0$, $t=t_0$. As seen from a frame moving with constant velocity $-v$, one has E', p', x', t' such that the Lorentz invariant holds:

$$A = -Et + px = -m\phi c^2 t_0 = -E't' + p'x' \text{ with } x'/t' = v \quad ((9))$$

One may note that $dA=0$ if $t' = \hbar/E'$ and $x' = \hbar/p'$. Even though $x'/t' = v$, the form $-Et + px$ treats them as independent, but they can change (i.e there can be a frequency and wavelength) such that A remains constant. The Lorentz invariant yields $dA/dx \text{ partial} = p$ and $dA/dt \text{ partial} = -E$ so creating eigenvalue equations yields $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-iEt)$. The fact that one may use frames with discrete v values means that one may have one frame in which one sees E_1, p_1 . A frame moving relative to this may see E_2, p_2 etc. Thus one may create a final E, p using various series of frames. This again leads to the idea of probability because any series of frames should have the same overall probability. There is no preference for a series of frames This again leads to the statistical rule $P(E_1)P(E_2) = P(E_1+E_2)$ etc.

Comparison with Classical Statistical Mechanics

One may note the similarity of $\exp(ipx)$ or $\exp(-Et)$ with $\exp(-e_i/T)$ from the Maxwell-Boltzmann factor. This similarity exists because both follow the statistical rule:

$$P(\text{variable 1}) P(\text{variable 2}) = P(\text{variable 1} + \text{variable 2}) \quad ((9))$$

This begs the question: Why are there two forms: $\exp(-iEt)$ and $\exp(-E/T)$ where T =temperature, if both contain energy. In the case of an MB case, one distributes energy, thus one may consider a two body elastic collision: $e_1+e_2 = e_3+e_4$ and $f(e_1)f(e_2) = f(e_3)f(e_4) = f(E=e_1+e_2=e_3+e_4)$. Thus the general statistical rule ((6)) applies to both $\exp(-iEt)$ and $\exp(-E/T)$. In the MB case, one does not ask how E was created (i.e which set of impulses created it i.e what was its history?). Rather one is interested in the history of two body collisions. E_1 collides with E_2 to create a total energy of E_1+E_2 which then may break into different E_i, E_j sets such $E_i+E_j = E_1+E_2$. Thus the sets here are combination sets of E_i 's and there is a total amount of energy available. $\exp(-E/T)$ with T being associated with the total amount of kinetic energy

becomes the probabilistic value. If one considers a single E_i and is interested in its history then one obtains $\exp(i E b^2)$ where we have argued that b^2 becomes the variable time in order to bypass contradictions involved in $dx \rightarrow 0, dt \rightarrow 0$.

Thus in both the MB case and $\exp(-Et)$, the form $\exp(-E b)$ is associated with a kind of history of interaction which allows for the erasure of this history. For the MB case, $\exp(-E_1/T)\exp(-E_2/T) = \exp(-E/T)$ and now any $E_i + E_j = E$ may be used. For $\exp(-iEt)$, the final E may be obtained through a set of discrete impulse changes with corresponding dE changes, but all that matters is the final energy state. For product probabilities this implies $\exp(-iEt)$. "i" is used to make the function periodic because it cannot grow infinitesimally or become 0.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that although Newtonian mechanics treats x and t symmetrically in: Impulse = Integral $F dt$ and Work = Integral $F dx$, these two functions equal Integral dp and Integral $v dp$ which are completely different in nature. Integral dp allows for discrete changes in p and hence is linked with probability because one may create a p through different sets of impulses $\{p_1, p_2, p_3\}$ or $\{p_4, p_5\}$ or another and each set has the same overall probability weight. Integral $v dp$, however, must integrate over x, t ranges because if p were to change discretely, what v should be used? Thus Integral $v dp = pp/2m$ is associated with deterministic acceleration from $v=0$ to $v=p/m$ (nonrelativistically). In other words x and t must change and this occurs according to $x(t)$. This, however, leads to a contradiction. For an impulse, one thinks of $dt \rightarrow 0$ with Integral $F dt = \text{finite}$, but the resulting p must be associated with $pp/2m$ which implies an x and t range. Thus one may introduce an x range, but it is independent of t . In other words, it must be probabilistic.

This at first seems highly unusual, but given that different sets of impulses may create a given p and all have the same weight, the probability rule $P(p_1)P(p_2) = P(p_1+p_2)$ must hold. This leads to $\exp(i p b)$ as the probability associated with p where b is a constant. Changing b to x yields $\exp(ipx)$ or the required probability distribution. We give similar arguments for $\exp(-pp/2m t)$.

These same results follow from considering the special relativistic invariant $A = -Et + px$.

Finally, both $\exp(-E/T)$ i.e. the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution and $\exp(ipx)$ or $\exp(-iEt)$ follow from the same statistical rule, but are involved in the "erasure" of different microscopic histories, retaining only an overall history. In the MB case, one is interested in two body collisions so one ultimately wants $f(E_1)f(E_2) = f(E_1+E_2)$. In other words the specific microscopic history of the collision is erased as $E_1+E_2 = E_3+E_4 = E$ means one has the same probability for (E_1, E_2) and (E_3, E_4) . This in turn means $f(E) = C \exp(-E/T)$. In the case of $\exp(-iEt)$ different impulse hits lead to different sets of $\{dE_i\}$ such that Sum over $i dE_i = E$. One is not interested in the specific microscopic history of impulses, only in the final result, so the form $\exp(-iEt)$ yields this form. The added feature is that instead of the parameter $1/T$ (T =temperature) one has the variable t as there is both a probability distribution in t and x which are independent i.e. $\exp(-ipp/2m t)$ and $\exp(ipx)$ in order to allow for an impulse Integral $F dt$ with $dt \rightarrow 0$ to be consistent with $pp/2m$ i.e. have both a dt and dx range, although these two are independent. We argue that $\exp(-Et)$ and $\exp(ipx)$ carry the history of the creation of p although it is a history based on the initial point and

the final, not on the specific set of impulses which bring one from the initial to the final point. Thus even an impulse carries with it these initial-final point histories with them.